

An open-source web-based solution for interactive assessment of accessibility via public transport

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Summary

This paper explores the implementation of an open-source web-based solution for dynamically evaluating the accessibility of services via public transport. The application aims to provide policymakers, service providers and transport managers with intuitive and highly interactive tools to help analyse and compare how access to services over public transport networks may be affected by proposed changes in the transport infrastructure, the placement of service delivery points, or timetable and routing modifications.

1. Introduction

Past research has shown that many current tools present only static outputs to practitioners and the public, and thus limit stakeholders to analysing only pre-selected or pre-analysed impacts (Wigan, 2016, p.228). Due to the complexity of public transit networks and their interactions with urban spaces, practitioners may be discouraged by the significant computational effort needed to compute actionable results, which ultimately can lead to less meaningful interaction in the planning process (Stewart & Zergas, 2016).

Aiming to address this research issue, this study explores the development of an interactive browser tool that allows existing public transport networks to be easily modified by the user in order to reveal their predicted impacts on local spatial accessibility patterns. By combining predictive analysis with spatial and aspatial accessibility measurements, users can then better assess the possible ramifications of proposed public transport changes and, by evaluating these results, determine which communities are most likely to be affected by the changes. This is particularly important given that in Wales, as elsewhere across the UK, the bus infrastructure currently appears to be in significant decline with the withdrawal of many routes over the last few years (Langford, et al, 2022). In a recent address to the climate change, environment, and infrastructure committee in the Welsh Senedd, one of the key issues

raised was the sustainability of bus services and how reduced government support has led to cuts in many services. Even in the ten years before the COVID-19 pandemic, Welsh passenger journeys had fallen from a total of 130 million to 101 million, with the reduction in government support being widely seen as one of the main drivers of this trend (Senedd Proceedings, 2023). The committee also highlighted that the most rural parts of Wales are at greatest risk, with bus services to these communities often not being commercially viable without additional support. This decline in transport opportunities may also coincide with the loss of local amenities (e.g. banks, schools, pharmacies), leading to a negative feedback cycle whereby further bus travel is then necessary to support everyday rural living. This research seeks to address this complex issue through the creation of an application that provides enhanced support for public transport practitioners, service providers, local stakeholders, and even the general public, allowing them to proactively assess the potential impacts of any anticipated changes to public transport infrastructure on accessibility to key services.

2. Research aims and objectives

The primary objective of this research is to develop a free open-source tool that allows its users to intuitively interact with spatial data whilst providing functionality to accurately determine and report geographical accessibility to services. Such a tool has the potential to provide an important bridge between academic and industry use (Pajares, et al, 2022), and may itself be a powerful advertisement and advocate for the usefulness of similar tools operating outside of the academic setting (Silva et al, 2019). To achieve this main objective a focus is placed upon the delivery of functionality and features that can improve user analysis of data using only open-source tools. A particularly challenging capability, whose development is prioritised here, is allowing a user to construct or insert an entirely new bus route, and then investigate changes to local accessibility scores that it causes.

3. Methods

Figure 1 displays the core open-source components of the application developed, illustrating how they interact with each other in order to display useful information to the user. The back-end consists of a combination of Postgres/PostGIS and OpenTripPlanner (OTP). PostGIS is utilised to store and supply point-of-interest information to the application, which is subsequently combined with public transport timetable and routing data held in OpenTripPlanner, the point-of-interest data is sourced through ONS and Digimap making it available to researchers and academics however this data can easily be exchanged within the database for openly available data. Furthermore, OTP determines those areas that are reachable via public transport from a user-specified starting position and user-specified travel time limit, from which it is then possible to generate cumulative opportunity access scores. PHP is adopted as the scripting language providing communication and data transfer activities between the front and back end of the application. The result is that via the front-end browser, a user can configure

an on-the-fly request for calculations, these are posted to the back end which computes the results and returns the appropriate information for display back in the browser. The front end of the application consists essentially of Javascript coding that leverages the functionality of the Leaflet mapping and Chart.JS plotting libraries. The primary activity at the front-end is the visualisation and presentation of data generated from PostGIS and OpenTripPlanner. Leaflet is tasked with displaying the travel time data in the form of a highlighted set of isochrone polygons, and Chart.js is deployed for presenting cumulative opportunity scores for each selected point of interest type. As well as visualising data, the front-end also allows user interactivity, so that users can request and tailor the calculations of interest. The system currently includes functionality to: temporarily remove selected bus routes; temporarily remove selected bus stops; reset the starting location via a postcode search; select the timetable dataset to be used (in terms of the month and year it was published); and the facility or points of interest class that is to be included in the output accessibility scores.

Figure 1- shows the core parts of the application.

4. Implementation of features within the application

Further to the list of functionality described above, one of the most technically challenging features to be implemented in this application is a user-friendly interface and environment facilitating easy amendment (adding, modifying and deleting) of bus service routes (the entire set of service access points that a transit line provides), trips (a specific instance of a vehicle travelling along the route) and stops (the points of entry and departure). Early iterations of the application made use of

OpenTripPlanner 1.5 to generate public transport isochrones from a user-defined starting location or from the POI itself. A topical example of how a potential transport planner could utilise the application is the measurement of the recent 20mph enforcements within Wales and how this has affected bus accessibility (Figures 2 & 3). When utilising OTP 1.5 a user can measure the potential impacts by looking at the accessibility scores as well as the isochrone polygon on the map allowing users to analyse the effects of bus timetable changes. A major limitation of this approach is that OTP demands the transport topology graph be pre-computed and pre-loaded as a static object before analyses can commence. This limitation effectively prohibits the ability to implement functionality that supports the addition of new bus routes.

Figure 2- Bus accessibility in North Wales before 20mph speed limit change

Figure 3- Bus accessibility in North Wales after 20mph speed limit change

One potential solution to this problem is the adoption of the “R5” routing engine, as developed by Conveyal, as a substitute for OTP. R5 was developed by the same original contributors as OTP and is offered as an open-source library. Critically, it generates a new graph before each calculation, thereby allowing edits to be applied to the source GTFS data. Through the adoption of R5 as the routing engine users may now add new bus routes prior to conducting their accessibility calculations. The integration of R5 is only specifically for the addition of bus routes other aspects of the application still rely on OTP, this is due to the computational speeds of both routing engines with basic and small calculations being faster through OTP due to it not having to generate the routing network before every calculation.

The functionality to insert, remove, or edit bus routes has the potential to assist policymakers in understanding the possible ramifications and any unintended consequences of proposed or anticipated public transportation changes. There is also the potential for such a system to be made available to the public, thus promoting the use of collaborative and participatory GIS. Members of local communities

could utilise this application to foresee possible impacts that any proposed changes to the bus infrastructure may have upon their own access to local points of interest (see Figure 4&5). Likewise, end-point service providers may find it informative and commercially valuable to have a better understanding of how their local market and client base might be affected by any such changes. The availability of this tool could thus enable local communities to generate statistical evidence and visualisations that would help support their arguments for crucial routes to be maintained and supported through government subsidies irrespective of their *prima facie* lack of commercial profitability.

Figure 4- Accessibility of an Arriva bus route in North Wales that has plans to be removed.

Figure 5- Accessibility from the same location but with the planned route change enacted.

In addition to adding and deleting bus routes, the application developed here also provides multiple levels of analysis via features that let its users create, edit and delete service points of interest on the map. These too can have numerous spatial and aspatial effects on the local patterns of service accessibility. The system developed allows details such as site opening times or capacity constraints to be adjusted in order to evaluate the effects such changes may exert on overall accessibility. As noted before with transport routes, this functionality can facilitate cooperative GIS and promote investigative analysis. This feature allows significant sophistication to be incorporated into the analyses undertaken, for example by ensuring that only those service delivery points that are open at the calculation time are included within the accessibility score. Service access levels can be further explored within the application by adopting transport timetables associated with different months, allowing users to identify temporal trends and provide a more contextual view of a specific location.

5. Future work and conclusion

Whilst considerable functionality is already available in the application developed to date, future work will experiment with the adoption of live GTFS data feeds that are being made available from the UK Government's bus open data service. This could supply the application with live positional data of buses and thus confirm the accuracy of isochrones currently constructed from static bus timetable data. This would build on recent research into the actual position of buses in Bristol and Leeds as compared to their timetables (Forth, 2023). This work has revealed a large discrepancy between realised and revealed data and confirms that bus services are often not as reliable as their timetables may imply. This development would give this application the ability to allow 'true' real-time accessibility insights within local communities. In addition to live GTFS feeds, further development work is intended on the user interface. From the outset, the needs and typical activities of transport planners have been considered when designing the user interface, which should encourage its future uptake. There are also plans for workshops to be run in order to demonstrate the possible benefits of utilising the application amongst potential stakeholders including members of the public. To gain valuable insight into further improvements a workshop will be conducted in which potential users can evaluate and provide feedback on the current effectiveness of the tool. Moreover, a live demonstration of the application has been planned at attending events to further gather data on how users interact the application and gather feedback on possible improvements. Furthermore, since the application is constructed upon open-source tools the code and all assets vital to the application will be published to GitHub upon the completion of the PhD ensuring the application stays open-source.

To conclude, the application created thus far has succeeded in meeting its primary research aims. The functionality currently implemented allows both spatial and aspatial on-the-fly interactive analysis of public transport accessibility, which can be used to identify areas lacking access to crucial services or to assess how access might be degraded, enhanced, or otherwise affected by potential changes to transport and service configurations. The ability to remove a bus route allows the user to explore the possible ramifications of public transport changes before being implemented and may provide an opportunity for local stakeholders to protest and argue against such changes with the aid of evidential support. Likewise, the ability to add new bus routes allows users to map and better understand its possible benefits, presenting associated accessibility scores that consider both spatial and aspatial factors. The application is developed as an accessible web application both open-source and free to use, making it invaluable to public transport planners and stakeholders alike as it provides the means to validate and scrutinise problematic public service changes in local communities.

6. Biographies

Liam Webb is a third-year PhD Student based in the Faculty of Computing, Engineering and Science, at the University of South Wales. His PhD is concerned with using web-based technologies to enhance the computation and visualisation of spatial accessibility to services.

Mitchel Langford is Professor of Spatial Analysis and Geoinformatics at the Faculty of Computing, Engineering and Science, University of South Wales, and a co-director of the Wales Institute of Social and Economic Research, Data and Methods (WISERD). His research interests include dasymetric mapping, accessibility modelling, geo-computation and applied geospatial analysis.

Gary Higgs is Professor of Geographical Information Science at the Faculty of Computing, Engineering and Science, University of South Wales, and a co-director of the Wales Institute of Social and Economic Research, Data and Methods (WISERD). Over-arching research interests are in the application of GIS in social and environmental studies, most recently in health geography and emergency planning.

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